

FORWARD

(GA 824550)

Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

WP4 - Capacity building and training activities

REPORT

**Deliverable 4.3 - Common training programme for
OR's R&I Officers**

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Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions

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INTRODUCTION

The deliverable 4.3 (D4.3), Common training programme for OR's R&I Officers highlights the importance of the training and capacity building of the OR's R&I Officers as a part of a process of capacitation previewed in the Work package 4 of the FORWARD project (GA 824550), "Fostering research excellence in EU Outermost Regions". The goal of this deliverable is described in the GA as "A common training programme for ORs' R&I actors will be developed to provide a common basis for the implementation of capacity building activities for R&I actors in the 9 regions."

The D4.3 is dedicated to develop a "common basis" of capacity building activities, namely trainings and fellowships (advanced trainings), targeting R&I Officers with the objective to improve competences in the Research and Innovation (R&I) Framework Programmes (FP), European in general, and to foster international cooperation and outreach. This deliverable aims to create a "common training programme for ORs' R&I officers to develop the common services expected from the ORs' Officers" including technical support to advise and orient R&I actors in EU R&I Framework Programmes."

The Deliverable 4.3 includes two tasks for the OR's Officers, Task 4.3. Establishment of a network of dedicated OR R&I Officers (18-36) and Task 4.4 Capacity Building for OR's Officers as follow:

[Task 4.3. Establishment of a network of dedicated OR R&I Officers \(18-36\)](#)

The FORWARD Grant Agreement (GA) presents a proposal to create a regional support mechanism to be connected to a OR Officers network that could complement the National Contact Points from the EU R&I Programmes considering the peculiarities and features from the OR's. This WP aims at creating the conditions for the establishment of trained and well-prepared OR R&I Officers network in order to support and raise awareness, be a point of dissemination and promote the knowledge on European Framework Programmes as well as other EU funds for Research and Innovation.

Each OR region will implement the Capacity plans through their regional governments, as this task involves political decisions and political budget allocation from the OR's regional governments and national governments as well, to go beyond the capacity of the FORWARD project reach of implementation. FORWARD aims to provide training for regional Officers and prepare them to support the R&I actors participating in the European Programs as well as to provide governments with scientific

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based information. In this aspect the WP4 leader has made a robust R&I ecosystem analysis to identify the needs and intended training, collecting information and the vision of the regional authorities and NCP (with a national and European vision). This information may contribute to build awareness and an initial plan to set up and structure a network for OR's R&I Officers.

As referenced in this document, the WP's actions within the project have also an important role in empowering and completing the process for implementation of an OR's R&I Officers network, as the complementary actions from the FORWARD's Work Packages foreseen tasks.

Task 4.4 Capacity Building for OR's Officers

This task will aim at providing the OR's Officers teams with the necessary training and expertise to develop the services expected from the OR's Officers, namely:

- Understanding the specificities of their R&I ecosystems to provide a customized guidance on choosing relevant H2020 topics and types of action;
- Advice on administrative procedures and contractual issues;
- Training and assistance on proposal writing;
- Distribution of documentation (forms, guidelines, manuals etc.);
- Assistance in partner search promoting international networking activities and collaborations.

These trainings will be done in the context of the proposed action plans of FORWARD project and in close collaboration with the NCPs of each Member state and taking into account the outputs of the FORWARD thematic working groups. This task allows, for example, the link and participation of the OR's Officer team at the European and National Open Days.

The deliverable 4.3 ("Common training programme for OR's R&I officers") follows up the report of D4.1 (M18) on "Capacity building plan", in which all the OR's started the process of capacity strategy oriented by the WP4 methodology, presented by the WP4 leader. This process involved the analyzes of the data collected in a bottom up approach under the WP2 and as well their main outputs, the joint strategy and the process of design and organization of the Thematic Working Groups on the WP3. The WP2 conclusions, the diagnosis, the state of the art of the R&I communities including needs and strengths plasmed in the joint strategy were the basis for the presented 9 Regional Capacity trainings.

The Capacity Plan for FORWARD is dedicated to build skills and capacities for improving the OR's participation in Framework Programs (FP) and it is oriented to the quadruple helix target. This deliverable highlights two tasks of the OR's Officers including the present and future sources of sustainable capacitation of the OR's R&I actors.

The existence of dedicated services providing assistance dedicated to FP support and other R&I financing in the EU for local stakeholders, namely to build, manage and report on projects, is an asset to increase regional participation in EU financed programmes and promote the development of regional research and innovation.

One among many other advantages of this support network, with regional representation, is the reduction of the entry costs to Horizon 2020. It allows participants to focus on scientific aspects of the proposal and its development cycle. It also promotes local stakeholder's commitment and interest and contributes to increased participation in the FP as it, consequently, strengthens the integration of the OR's in the European Research Area. In the context of the WP4, it has foreseen the following deliverables to be submitted:

Deliverable Number	Deliverable Title	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D4.1	Capacity building plan	Report	Public	M18-M19¹
D4.2	Common training programme for OR's R&I actors	Report	Public	M18-M22
D4.3	Common training programme for OR's R&I officers	Report	Public	M25
D4.4	OR R&I Offices Operational and Sustainability Strategic for implementation	Report	Public	M36

Table1 – Deliverables from the FORWARD WP4

¹ *D4.1 and D4.2 suffered delay due to COVID context

VISION AND STATE OF THE ART

Methodology of construction

To build the D4.3, the WP4 has resourced to several information's, by taking in to account the providers and beneficiaries of this action, by using previous analyzed information from the WP2 diagnose and mapping reports and base information, such as the FP7 table, on Support Services Mapping and the mutual learning event conclusions, as well as the Joint Strategy (D2.5) orientations on this thematic, as well resourcing to the consultation of national and regional entities regarding the skills and role of the OR's R&I Officers.

The OR's R&I Officers role, existence depends on political awareness of their importance, as well as political priorities and financial availability. However the FORWARD project, supported by scientific-based information -obtained by analyzing data and following the consultation of the relevant stakeholders-, can give information that can be used as the basis for political decisions, at a European, national, and regional levels. The methodology was developed following this approach in order to use previous information regarding the stakeholders of the R&I ecosystem, as well as providing new information at other levels of the OR's so that it will give a wider and more representative vision on the role and relevance of OR's R&I Officers. On the one hand, the process of the state-of-art of the OR's R&I Officers can contribute to identifying stakeholders that already are working on the OR's R&I ecosystem and that can benefit from this capacity plan. On the other hand, it can identify the need for an organization and R&I Officers at regional level that can promote the successful participation in Framework Programs and be part of/complete this network.

The WP4 leader, in the spirit of collaboration and co-construction with the OR's partners in this project, requested the collaboration of the Regional Coordinators for WP4, representing the 9 OR's partners in the project (table 1) to gather the following different levels of data:

Support services in OR's

The identification on the 9 regional support services ("FP-7 Support Services" from D2.2 report - WP2) has provided an analysis on the deliverable 4.3 by identifying the existing Support Services in some of the OR's.

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These identified structures can work as a support to mutual learning in FP Participation, not only at the level of the OR's R&I ecosystem, as within the Forward consortium, that can act as platforms for connection between OR's R&I actions and stakeholders.

Questionnaire for NCP and Regional governments

This questionnaire with the same set of questions targeted two decisional levels, on the one hand at a national/European level and on the other, at regional level. The questions were meant for obtaining answers to launch a reflection and to bring awareness on the importance of decentralized services for the follow-up of the R&I communities in OR's, but also to state the impact that this swift may have on the regions. The answers allowed us, as OR's, to have a combined vision that focuses on the OR Officers important role and its needs for training and its expected impact at a level of organizations with different decision and influence levels.

Training and capacity Building for the OR's R&I Officers

The selection/extraction of training and capacity actions from the Regional Capacity Plan that targets OR Officers allowed to seek for common features and trends on capacity and skills training according to the different needs of each OR's realities. As it was already concluded in the different reports from the FORWARD project (D2.2; D2.5; D4.1; D4.2, among others), the OR's have to adjust approaches by their own singularities and heterogeneities, despite its common outermost region characteristics.

Gathering the existing information and pairing it with the new information collection allowed the WP4 leader to have a report that includes science based information (mapping and diagnose) combined with the view of the main organizations whose policies can contribute to the R&I stakeholders to gain better access to the EC programs.

The synergies to co-construct this report are defined in a way that each designated Regional Coordinator (table 2) contributes to the report content, as a network of knowledge that gives a picture of the common situation of the OR's R&I community, as well as its differences. Coordinated synergies that contribute to a common implementation for the benefit of the OR's R&I ecosystem.

FORWARD WP4 Regional Coordinators		
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Table 2. Regional Coordinators contacts for WP4, in representation of the OR's in the FORWARD project

Objectives for the Capacity Actions for OR's Officers

The following objectives will help to align the level of expertise to the existing needs in order to transform the OR's R&I Officers into a network of agents of innovation and research excellence prepared to support the FP development in the 9 OR's. Therefore, we would like to suggest a common programme, according to specific objectives for our community:

Objective 1 : Boosting stakeholders' interest for collaborative Research & Innovation at EU level

Capacity action for Officers 1 : How to build a communication strategy which creates the will to participate?

Objective 2: Supporting Researchers in getting new habits to increase their connection capacities

Capacity action for Officers 2 : Acting like a coach creates the will to participate?

Objective 3: 100% of capable researchers involved in connection activities at EU level s

Capacity action for Officers 3 : How to detect promising candidates among the community ?

Objective 4: : Boosting private companies participation in Horizon 2020

Capacity action for Officers 4 : Mastering EU opportunities for companies

Objective 5: Developing participation through less used or new instruments

Capacity action for Officers 5: Mastering Widening and MSCA programmes

Objective 6: Increasing the visibility of OR's research and Innovation in the calls

Capacity action for Officers 6: How to build a lobbying strategy to integrate OR's topics in the work programmes

Objective 7: Increasing quality of proposals

Capacity action for Officers 7: Original/Innovative ideas for impact and implementation sections

Objective 8: Mastering horizontal issues for EU projects

Capacity action for Officers 8: Master specific thematic in EU projects, as Gender, Ethics, Open data, Responsible Research & Innovation, ...

The combination and *crescendum* of these objectives creates a clear roadmap for the planning and implementation of capacity building actions for the OR R&I Officers, to be adapted to the level of expertise of the different OR's.

The FP support services in the OR's

The initiated analysis of the existing support services available for the R&I actors in the OR's was launched by NEXA, as WP2 leader (diagnose and mapping), with the FP7 Support Service Table in the context of the deliverable 2.2.

As indicated in the *Nine regional diagnosis and joint strategy for OR R&I ecosystem performance (D2.2)*, the existence of dedicated FP support services, dedicated to provide assistance to local stakeholders in the full length of the projects, from finding the calls to managing the project, is an important asset to increase regional participation in FP programmes. It reduces the entry costs to Horizon 2020 and allows participants to focus on scientific aspects of the proposal development cycle. It also reflects local stakeholder's commitment to increase participation in FP and thus strengthen the integration of their region in the European Research Area.

To support mutual learning within the FORWARD consortium, the "FP-7 Support Services" template, in FP Participation aims at describing the service supports in place in the regions (objectives, activities and services, achievements and results). In order to fill out this template, partners can contact regional support services representatives. Beyond the description, partners are invited to question FP facilitators about difficulties revealed in their daily practice alongside project leaders and collect good practices.

On 7 out of 9 OR's indicated the existence of such support services in their OR's as indicated in graphic 1.

Graphic 1. Number of Support Services per OR based on the FP7 table from WP2 diagnose and mapping (NEXA collected data)

From the collected information, besides the number it was also possible to investigate the type of services, either it's public, private or other types of infrastructure, as associations for example. This information allows us to have a better idea regarding the type of available support in the OR's to the R&I actors and how engaged is the public sector in the creation and promotion of such services and the importance given to the support to the R&I community. As well as the interest and involvement of the private sector and other actors of the OR's R&I. The non-public infrastructures services can contribute with a different kind of services, mostly not free of charge; nevertheless, it is an option available therefore, it is positive that they exist parallel to public options, with the offering of complementary services. We can see visual analyses of the type and number of support services illustrated in graphic 2.

Graphic 2. Number per type of Support infrastructures type per OR, on R&I services. Based on the FP7 table from WP2 diagnose and mapping (NEXA collected data)

It's important to analyze also the support targeted by these infrastructures in order to conclude either the specific support for some actors is being taken into consideration or is it just a general support and what this brings into the light regarding the importance and relevance given to these R&I actors. The main support is given to all the R&I ecosystems, but a large part is also targeted to SME's and the private sector.

There isn't an overwhelming number of support infrastructures directed specifically to researchers, as we would probably initially expect, as these fall into the general support category, as it's possible to verify in graphic 3 regarding the target public of the R&I support infrastructures in OR's.

Graphic 3. Target public of the Support infrastructures on R&I services, per type, in the OR. Based on the FP7 table from WP2 diagnose and mapping (NEXA collected data)

Establishment of the network OR's R&I Officers

Taking in consideration some OR's already have OR R&I Officers working in an informal way in R&I infrastructures, namely Universities and public organizations, we should look at the OR's R&I Officers network not just in a perspective of creation, as also a matter of identification and linking the already exist OR's R&I Officers in the OR's and promoting their identification and network with other peer, OR R&I Officers, in the OR's. The existing structures and OR's Officers in the regions could be the starting point to build such a network. This network should promote equal, consistent and more customized support to regional research and innovation actors' participation in Research Framework Programmes and set similar approaches and goals to reach this goal and promote more participation in FP programs. The advantages of this reorganization/creation support on the spot, regionally, and in the applicants' own languages.

Professional support services operating regionally would form an essential component of Funding Programmes implementation by spreading awareness, giving specialist advice, and providing on-the-ground guidance, they will ensure that the different EU Funding Programmes become known and accessible to any potential applicants, from every sector or area.

In order to implement this action, specially the OR's R&I Officers network (Task 4.3), it's fundamental that the synergies between WP5 and WP6 work, in order to piggy-back on activities, contacts, discussions, policy briefs and official agreements to establish all necessary conditions for the fully commitment of each Regional Government to implement an OR's R&I office. Having the signature of a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) by every region for the Network of OR R&I Officers will be the main outcome to this common OR's strategy towards the promotion of the OR's R&I ecosystems.

[NCP's priorities and vision for the OR's R&I Officers](#)

France

According to the exchange with NCPs it was highlighted that the need for the OR's to be more present and represented in the Thematic Working Groups and European networks. This will enable the needs and specificities of our overseas territories to be expressed in advance so that they can be taken into account in the various calls for projects.

They note a lack of efficiency in disseminating information on European programmes from the Ministry of Research to the overseas territories and are ready to remedy this by organizing specific training courses (webinar, info-day, etc.).

They call for a strengthening of the capacities of universities and ecosystem actors in our regions by linking higher education to research and innovation issues, particularly social innovation. This also involves promoting the careers of researchers involved in European projects.

Finally, the setting up of a European cell would provide a real relay for transmitting information and support project leaders. Given the size of the organizations in our territories, they believe that this cell should be led by the regional authorities and federate all the players (universities, research organizations, companies). It could even be considered to have a single cell per large region for Martinique and Guadeloupe.

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The NCPs, namely the NCP for SMEs, highlighted that that the Ministry of Research and Higher Education has launched an action plan "PAPFE" to improve the participation of French stakeholders in FP². This action plan will change the way NCPs are implemented ("Reforme") in order to have more coordinated actions between NCPs to avoid "fragmentation". One NCP will be dedicated to Widening/Cost/ERA. This NCP will be more active than the previous Widening NCP. The NCP will develop more online activities and actions will better take into considerations the level of knowledge of stakeholders. The NCPs will provide more capacity building activities (through specific modules).

The action plan also foresees the setup of regional networks with a regional referent in contact with the NCPs, which will remain national points. A dialogue between Europe Offices from organisms belonging to the same territory will also be encouraged.

Regarding the SME and private companies, a report on their participation in H2020 was performed and establishes recommendations for the next programming period. The report shows that, at the national level, there are 50 FTE providing support for SMEs to participate in Horizon 2020. 3 main types of organizations are offering such support: Regional development/innovation agencies «pôles de compétitivité» (national clusters); Chambers of commerce.

The main recommendations for Horizon Europe are:

- a) Support should be region-specific, structured and supported by regional authorities to avoid fragmentation, duplication, competition and lacks;
- b) Support should be organized through a regional complementary network, led by an organization with expertise in Framework Programmes support;
- c) Support should be performed by organizations which have a good knowledge of private sectors and their R&I needs and ambition, have the capacity to expertise the state of the art;
- d) A FP Officer should be able to provide: information, orientation, diagnostic, partner search, connexion with FP consultancies, proposal writing support.

² <https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/cid152062/le-plan-d-action-national-d-amelioration-de-la-participation-francaise-aux-dispositifs-europeens-de-financement-de-la-recherche-et-de-l-innovation.html>

PORTUGAL

From the Portuguese NCP view, the OR's R&I Officers are very much welcome to take part of the National Promotion Network, integrated in the PERIN - Portugal in Europe R&I Network. This recent network was established recently to support the internationalization of R&I and, therefore, to boost the Portuguese participation in the European funding programmes (Horizon Europe, European Space Program, Digital Europe, Connecting Europe2, Erasmus+, among others).

Regarding the importance for the implementation of FORWARD goals and legacy, the Portuguese NCP declared that despite some geographical distance from the most active R&I hubs, the OR R&I Officers can play an essential role in promoting and improving OR's excellence in R&I, as well as in the articulation of R&I activities with the local territorial development.

The NCP affirmed that the OR's R&I Officers are in a better position to know and understand the regional situation, as well as their interests and problems, so this local support would certainly make a difference.

In terms of the base capacity skills for OR's R&I Officers, ideally, the NCP referred to the capabilities/skills should replicate those existing in the centralized offices at national level, with whom a strong collaboration should be established, with an emphasis on regional priorities.

SPAIN

The CSIC, EU-Officer and H2020 NCP, as replied in representation of the NCP in Spain. They see the OR's Officers or Regional Contact Points (RCP) as a local source for advice and information on Framework Programmes and the importance of the OR's R&I Officers is their expertise and knowledge on how to develop and manage a project. They also hold program events throughout the year in cooperation with NCPs. Together they could offer a wide array of services, which includes support for potential beneficiaries, in the form of advisory and training services, assistance for individual scientists, institutions, enterprises and any other entities interested in participating in the Framework Programmes.

In Spain, they already have implemented this model, since there is already in place regional innovation Agencies, like AAC (*Agencia Andaluza del Conocimiento*) depending on the Andalusian Regional Government, who has an thematic Officer's network that works in close cooperation with NCPs network, producing a multiplier effect of the information.

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For Spanish NCP the OR's R&I Officer should be knowledgeable about all aspects of Framework Programmes, "beyond their specialization area, thereby allowing effective signposting in line with the principle of 'no wrong door'"³. They should at least be aware of opportunities provided by related programs (eg. ESIF), good communicators, and be able to adapt methods as necessary, taking into account the diversity of actors that make up their constituency (eg. academia, industry, including SMEs, public authorities etc).

Regarding the integration of these OR's R&I Officers, the NCP expressed that they should be EU-Officers from Universities and Research Institutes, or Innovation Relay Centres (Industry oriented), preferably integrated in Regional Innovation Agencies and one officer for each horizontal or thematic program.

Spanish NCP defends that the thematic priorities targeted by the OR Officers in the Regional Innovation ecosystem should be based in the RIS3 definition process, since this process already identified a range of thematic priority areas for investments in every region. Interregional cooperation is essential for smart specialization – innovation often depends on exchanges and indirect effects from cooperation between clusters or knowledge hubs, and research and innovation networks are increasingly global. They argue that the regional innovation systems cannot be considered in isolation, and smart specialization should involve an identification of priorities and forms of collaboration between regions. OR officers should promote interregional and international synergies, complementarities and collaboration.

OR'S R&I Regional political structures priorities and vision for the OR's R&I Officers

CANARY ISLANDS

Role & actions

Canary Islands (CA) see the OR's officers or Regional Contact Points (RCP), as the local link between R&D&I community and European (Commission, Support offices), National (Ministries, NCPs) and Regional (Government, Regional Agencies) institutions to provide advice and information on Framework Programmes, proposal preparation and project management.

In their view the OR's Officers are important for the implementation of FORWARD goals and legacy, taking into account that the OR's or RCP may provide advice to the new Thematic working groups community

³CSIC, EU-Officer and H2020 NCP

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created within WP3. They may offer their expertise and knowledge on how to build new consortia, training services, assistance for individual scientists, institutions, enterprises and any other entities interested in participating in the next Horizon Europe program or others.

Competences & thematic priorities

According to Canary Islands, capacitation for OR's Officer can make a difference since it allows them to keep them updated and promote professional skill on languages and communication together with a deep knowledge about EU project development and management skills are important to provide effective advice to the end users. The base capacities in CA vision for OR's R&I Officers are mainly 3: (i) Deep knowledge about EU Framework Programmes and funding opportunities; (ii) Project preparation and management; (iii) Communication skills.

For CA the Thematic priority areas for each OR's are/should be in line with those thematic priorities in their respective institution and should be aligned with both regional RIS3 strategy and R&D strategy.

Integration: where and how many

Presently the OR's Officers or Regional Contact Points (RCP) are integrated in Universities and Research Institutes with good success. According to their experience the number of these R&I Officers should be defined according to the users demand in each institution.

AZORES

Role & actions

According to Azores vision an OR Officer will provide to the regional R&I actors information, networking and assistance, in their national language, regarding EU Research and Innovation (R&I) funds, especially in the context of the new Framework Programme. The objective is to approach the European R&I Agenda to the regional R&I ecosystems providing capacity actions and tools, in order to cover needs and support in the identification of networks and topics to participate in calls and developing impactful proposals.

Azores think that OR's R&I Officers are important for the implementation of FORWARD goals and legacy since they will capitalize the work and results of the FORWARD Project at two levels: regionally and between the ORs Officers networks. The main OR's R&I Officers tasks will include dissemination and awareness of the Framework Programmes, as regarding the importance and added value for the OR's and

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as well as supporting the local actors on the identification, submission and follow up of their financed EU projects in R&I. The main legacy of FORWARD is the capacitation and identification of these OR R&I Officers, taking advantage of the existing regional R&I institutions. The existence of the OR's R&I Officers and the network will allow a close link with the other OR's and a better identification of the opportunities for financing strategic joint projects promoting the excellence and strengthening the position of the OR's in the EU.

Competences & thematic priorities

Azores states that the capacity actions will help the OR's R&I Officers to improve their knowledge, skills, tools and a wider view of the R&I funding opportunities, with focus on the Framework Programme. More prepared and skilled Officers will contribute to a more efficient and active R&I ecosystem, with better chances of being involved and increase the OR's participation in FP initiatives and projects. OR's R&I Officers should have as base capacities/skills an integrated vision, with a strong knowledge of Region R&I ecosystem including the state of art and its players and as well with a richness network of the EU R&I System and Policy in order to link the conditions to the opportunities. The OR's R&I Officers skill should include communication capacities for stakeholder's engagement and awareness with specific target audiences, researchers, SMES, and wide audiences following the quadruple helix as target. OR's R&I Officers will domain all processes of the Framework Programme, from the Work Programs development to the call launch and proposals submission, in close cooperation with the national contact points. Regarding the projects life-cycle the ORs could provide support and advice to the OR's actors from the identification to the submission and managing of EU financed projects, at a technical and financial level and other transversal issues relevant for EU projects, as Gender, Ethics, Open data, Responsible Research & Innovation.

The Azores states that the OR R&I Officers target should follow the thematic topics covered under the new Framework Programme, Horizonte Europe. The exercises will be to link the European financing Programme priorities to the OR's -identified strategic areas identified in the FORWARD project mapping and diagnose (WP2) and based on the OR's capacities, R&I policies, Regional Smart Specialization Strategies-S3. This approach will give the OR's better chances to keep up with the trends at EU level and be more competitive and specialized R&I ecosystems.

Integration: where and how many

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Taking in consideration the policy framework and the developed work and investment of the FORWARD project, the OR R&I Officers should be identified under the regional existing R&I institutions in the respective OR's, at an academic and public level that have responsibilities in the R&I, according to Azores position.

The number of OR R&I Officers should be defined at a political and strategic level, in coordination with the National Contact Points institutions, in order to ensure the government representative should be ensured. Other regional contact points could be identified based on facts: number of identified R&I infrastructures; size of the R&I ecosystem, namely the total number of researchers, SMES that work in the area of R&I, etc. The OR R&I Officers have to work at a transversal level, including the specialized strategic areas for the Region, at S3 level.

FRENCH GUIANA

Role & actions

According to French Guiana the OR's R&I Officers should have the following role:

- Develop research work plans based on project needs;
- Identify potential beneficiaries and build strong relationships with them;
- Develop grant proposals and assist with grant completion and submission processes;
- Perform daily supervision of research staff for assigned projects;
- Act as the primary contact for the research team for all questions and concerns; Attend meetings to share new ideas and discuss issues;
- Participate in recruitment, orientation, training, performance appraisal, promotion of Employees;
- Assist in the maintenance of the research database and the project website;
- Coordinate budget preparation and expenditure control activities with management;
- Review financial reports, process invoices and approve expenses.

In their vision the OR's Officers are important for the implementation of FORWARD goals and legacy because they will encourage and promote the development of European projects through Thematic watch on the funding programs covered by the service (Horizon Europe and Erasmus + as a priority), including through monitoring the work of relevant organizations and networks in the research and innovation areas covered. As well as targeted information for researchers / services / establishments on calls for European research, innovation and training projects. Another important responsibility is the

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organization of information and training sessions for the academic community, as well as having the ability to give personalized advice to project leaders.

It is done studies and contributions to the integration of French Guiana players in higher education and research and innovation in European networks, in particular through the search for partners.

The OR's Officers are expected also to give their contribution to the analysis and capitalization of project evaluation reports and to the construction and updating of procedures and tools to support the setting up of European research and training projects as part of the continuous improvement process for the service provided to the R&I community.

Competences & thematic priorities

French Guiana region representatives state that the capacities/skills for OR's Officers should be based on experience in support functions for research professions. The knowledge or experience appreciated in thematic areas are Mathematics or Information and Communication Sciences and Technologies or Materials Sciences. It's also important that they have knowledge of the European Union funding in the areas of research and innovation, and training Knowledge of the functioning of higher education and research in France and in Europe Mastery of the engineering of transnational projects (meeting deadlines, managing an international partnership, budgeting, structuring of proposals, etc.)

It is important that the OR's R&I Officers, according to French Guiana, have an excellent written and oral comprehension of English Very good relationship Ability to work in a team and in a network, as well as autonomy, initiative and force of proposal. As well as editorial skills Capacity for animation and organization of regional events and Educational qualities.

According to perspective from the region, the OR's Officers in French Guiana should have a focus on the following areas: Health, Energy, Biodiversity.

Integration: where and how many

The OR's R&I Officers, according to French Guiana, should be placed in the Universities and should be 3 or 4.

MADEIRA

Role & actions

According to Madeira Region, the support offices of the ORs should have the important role of disseminating, among the scientific and business community, all-important information about research projects. It should also support the entire community in the project application phases. This office should also be the link between the community and the Commission services, as well as having the role of supporting the search for international partners. Another important role of this type of Office should be training, through clarification sessions, workshops, etc.

It's mentioned by Madeira that in order to attract more research and innovation to each of the ORs, it is necessary to ensure that the scientific and business community receive more support, both in terms of training and of concrete support in the writing of projects, for example. Concerning the business community, support all throughout the project is essential. Another fundamental point, according to Madeira's vision, is the search for international partners for national projects and vice versa.

Competences & thematic priorities

Madeira highlights that the R&I offices in the ORs must have the following common competences: (i) knowledge and information about the open calls in various areas so that the community is informed in a timely manner; (ii) Project writing skills; (iii) Competence to support and monitor the development of projects; (iv) Skills in training and promoting workshops on this topic; (v) digital skills.

The thematic priorities to be targeted by the OR Officers should be the Smart specialization areas per Region, according to Madeira.

Integration: where and how many

The point of view of Madeira of the OR's R&I Officers is that they should be integrated in Regional Governmental agencies for research and development. In the specific case of Madeira, it should be ARDITI (FORWARD partner), whose majority of members are from the Regional Government and the University of Madeira.

Related to how many OR officers should the OR's have, it is mentioned that "it should be analyzed on a case-by-case basis", as the OR's have very specific conditions. In the case of Madeira that has an archipelago is constituted by 4 islands - Madeira island, Porto Santo and *Desertas* Islands, administered

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together with the separate archipelago of the *Selvagens* Islands, the research is almost entirely concentrated in one of the islands, Madeira island, being the most populated. Therefore, Madeira supports the idea that the OR's R&I Officers should be based on that island.

It's also mentioned the important role of FORWARD project as the first step to an impact that is expected to live beyond the lifetime of the project itself.

REUNION

Role & actions

Since 2013, La Reunion has set up a territorial/regional service available for any researcher or entrepreneur from La Reunion called "Europe Office", which is composed of European project experts and which supports local stakeholders in the connection with European partners through competitive R&I projects. These experts implement 3 types of activities : Coaching and Training of stakeholders regarding networking at EU level, competitive research and funding; Promotion of regional capacities towards EU institutions and networks; Support stakeholders in the Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe and LIFE proposal's development cycle (from identification of opportunities to the negotiation with EC)

The following answers are based on the FORWARD results (WP2 Regional diagnosis) as well as on the regional roadmap to European Research Area, designed in 2020 with the R&I community of La Reunion.

According to Reunion, the purpose of the officers should be to increase the integration of the R&I community into the ERA. To do so, they have to build their stakeholder's capacities, to promote them at EU level and support the development of proposals in response to competitive calls for projects.

These OR officers are a cornerstone of the Forward goals as they are experts of the connection to, and collaboration with European champions. In a time of global competition, collaboration has become an imperative. Sharing resources and efforts, exchanging knowledge and know-how, foster capacities and distinctive innovations that allow organizations and territories to survive and thrive. For the 9 outermost regions (OR), connection is thus vital. Because of their limited size, they lack the critical mass of talents and resources crucial to build competitive advantages. This in turn hinders their capacity to attract the needed resources, which flow to, and concentrate in, a few well- endowed European hubs. To counteract this self-reinforcing, exclusion mechanism that affects their research, innovation, and economic

dynamics, OR must tackle their relational isolation. They need to connect to the major European networks and hubs, which will increase their visibility, attractiveness and capacities.

Competences & thematic priorities

Reunion highlights that a major factor that hinders the participation of the region's researchers in FP is the phenomenon of self-eviction, with potential candidates who choose not to participate. One of the reasons for this self-evidence is the perception of a low return on investment between the resources mobilized to develop a project and the chances of success. To overcome this barrier, researchers need to be convinced of the added-value of the participation and to trust the support system. They must then have a very professional support, delivered by experts who master the FP "jargon", act as coach, and are able to adapt their support programmes to the capacities and realities (time) of their stakeholders. To do so, it is fundamental to keep these experts up-to-date in terms of FP evolution, to train them to act like coach (communication, motivation, self-perception, reluctance to change, etc.), and to ensure that they develop personalized and step-by-step support for their communities (diagnosis, work plan design, etc.). In terms of base capacities/skills for OR's R&I Officers, Reunion Island highlights the following: (i) knowledge : Mastering FP (structure, rules, organization); (ii) Coaching skills : Communication, Social psychology; (iii) EU project development and management skills: identification of Research and Innovation expertise of an individual, Identification of potential partners, design of a work plan for networking, design of work plan for proposal writing, support to proposal writing (enriching the quality of the excellence, impact and implementation sections).

La Reunion refers at the level of thematic focus of the OR's R&I Officers in the Regional & Innovation ecosystem should be in direct link with RIS3 domains defined in each region.

Integration: where and how many

The regional agencies for research, innovation and development are already providing these kinds of services. Besides their experience, such agencies are tightly connected to policy makers, enjoy dedicated resources and can provide their services to all types of stakeholders (researchers, entrepreneurs, public organizations).

These officers would be at the head of a regional support network comprising 3 types of stakeholders with complementary roles: the Officers as described above, Correspondents in the R&I institutions (trained to Horizon Europe, who could provide a first level information on the program and orient

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potential stakeholders to the officers), Ambassadors in research team/companies (who will promote the program and opportunities in their respective organizations). In terms of the number of OR's R&I Officers, Reunion proposes 2 to 3 Officers for an ecosystem such as La Reunion.

GADELOUPE

Role & actions

The role of an OR's R&I Officer is to contribute to organize the development of the territories' R&D resources, whether public or private, and propose sustainable solutions to better reconcile, in our regions, their activities with the European R&D agenda and opportunities, according to Regional Council of Guadeloupe.

It is important for our territories to be part of the accelerated transformation of our society and to multiply the actions in favor of the energy, digital and ecological transitions, for Guadeloupe's economy, R&I actions should contribute further to accelerate the appropriation of innovations by our SMES, as well as the digital transformation of our companies to make them more efficient.

Competences & thematic priorities

The OR's R&I Officers should constitute a highly qualified team of people with complementary skills in innovation and research management, communication, with a good knowledge of the European institutional context.

The expertise that should be covered by the OR's R&I Officers should be the main thematic research areas of the territory and working in public and private organizations.

Almost 70% of the research conducted in Guadeloupe is focused on health, agriculture, livestock and the environment, with much of the work being devoted to environment, plant, animal and human health issues. Those themes should remain the main target of the R&I officers.

Integration: where and how many

The Regional Council of Guadeloupe states that they are the appropriate public authority to lead the team, as they are responsible for the economic development and regional planning. However, they should also have R&I officers working within business organizations to ensure the transmission of good practice and short-circuit access to opportunities offered by the European Union. Under the leadership of the Regional Council, a team of 3 to 4 people with thematic expertise would be suitable for this purpose.

MARTINIQUE

Role & actions

According to Martinique Region the role of the OR's R&I Officers should be to offer decision-makers and R&I strategy as well as implement dedicated tools. The OR's R&I Officers play an important role in relays in the follow-up and implementation of the recommendations and proposals retained within the framework of FORWARD.

Competences & thematic priorities

The investment in OR's R&I Officers competences, with capacity actions, allows the promotion of skills of Research and Innovation managers and increases the know-how that promotes excellence and encourages participation in the framework programs.

The base capacity for OR's R&I Officers, according to Martinique, are: (i) Knowledge of the environment and the ecosystem; (ii) Knowledge of actors' strategies; (iii) Design of tools dedicated to R&I; (iv) Structuring of strategies and actions.

Martinique defends that the OR's R&I Officers should dedicate themselves to the following thematic: (i) Humanities and Social Sciences; (ii) Health; (iii) Tourism; (iv) Economy of the sea; (v) Biodiversity.

Integration: where and how many

According to Martinique the organizations in which the OR's R&I Officers should be integrated are national, European and international organizations able to promote their specificities.

MAYOTTE

Role & actions

According to the *Conseil Départemental de Mayotte*, the role of an OR's R&I officer is to turn the political objective into actions. The idea is to implement the action plan of the political priorities. According to these region representatives, the Forward project plays an important role to pursue and nourish the relationships towards the OR's R&I Officers that should last beyond the project lifetime and could for example perpetuate for years the capacity action plan activities that will be implemented during the FORWARD project.

Competences & thematic priorities

One of the priorities in Mayotte is to popularize the R&I activities and projects by informing the local stakeholders of European projects calls, supporting them in their innovation process. The OR's R&I officer

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should be the one who connects the local stakeholders to the European (or International) projects ecosystem and to be the link between local stakeholders to other OR's.

To reinforce and maintain capacities of these actors, the capacity actions could be the training that OR'S R&I officers need for their role of support to the local stakeholders. The more they are trained the better would succeed in their tasks.

For Mayotte, Agriculture, Social innovation, Tourism and Eco-tourism and Digital innovation are definitely the priorities areas that the OR's R&I Officers should focus on. Those are the thematic in which Mayotte region needs the most advances and has the least innovation opportunities. For instance, in Agriculture, R&I can bring some solutions to the local production that is insufficient to satisfy the local demand. In terms of Digital, the region has to continue its development in the access of broadband, in 2020, the majority of the island has no access to broadband. There are a lot to do in digitalization of public administration processes, for example, most of the legal documents cannot be asked by email or through an online platform. The thematic of social innovation is also very important, since a few years, Mayotte has started experiencing social innovation with CRESS association through projects like FANYA'LAB. This project supports the development and consolidation of long-lasting Social Solidarity Economy companies with high social added value.

Integration: where and how many

According to the regions representatives the OR's R&I Officers should be integrated in the *Departement Council of Mayotte*, in the division of innovation or/and ADIM (Development & Innovation Agency of Mayotte), not specifying the number of OR Officers.

SAINT MARTIN

Role & actions

The role of an OR's R&I Officer, according to Saint Martin authorities, is to set up support tools for project leaders and partners (preparatory phase and implementation phase), as well as allow regions without universities and research centers (which is the case of Saint Martin) to benefit from the support of such structures via an OR network. Their role is also to be an information channel, and to support and advise political decision-makers in terms of strategy. Saint. Martin recognizes a key role of FORWARD for these OR's

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R&I Officers, as they rely on the monitoring and implementation of the outputs resulting from the FORWARD project.

Competences & thematic priorities

For Saint Martin the capacity actions for OR's R&I Officers can make a difference since they will allow better support for strengthening the participation of the ORs in EU framework programmes. The difference can also be made through scientific solutions that will be provided to meet a need or solve a problem encountered by one or more of the ORs. As base capacities/skills for OR's R&I Officers, Saint Martin considers: a good knowledge of the ecosystem, the actors, the challenges, the strategies put in place; capacities to design adapted tools dedicated to R&I; high skills in proposals, in terms of strategic orientations.

As thematic priorities, Saint Martin considers that the OR's R&I Officers should focus on Climate change; Health; Tourism; Biodiversity; Economy of the sea; Circular economy and Digital innovation.

Integration: where and how many

Saint Martin believes that OR's R&I Officers should be integrated in regional, national, European and international organizations and the number of these actors could depend on the size of the region's ecosystem.

IMPLEMENTATION

The implementation of FORWARD capacity actions for OR's Officers should count on the already defined actions of capacitation previously defined in the D4.1 and D4.2 and taking into consideration regional, national and European sources of capacitation, outside the scope of the FORWARD project. As examples of sources, we can name the National contact points, the Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions or other EU projects, as well as national or regional training plans available to the OR R&I Officers. The synergies of capacitation between OR's is also encouraged as a way to promote the link and reinforce the network and mutual knowledge.

This deliverable foresees the Capacity building and supporting activities targeted at the OR Officers in the OR's in order to promote or reinforce the project management skills to attain technical capacities in FP for themselves as well to pass on to support their teams and interested stakeholders in the region. As

well as training the community in EU project management: train trainer, as a sustainable perspective of the impact of these actions that should go beyond the duration of the FORWARD project.

Taking into account the diagnosed heterogeneity between the OR's ecosystem critical mass and maturity it's important that a common plan takes into consideration principles of equity that are important to increase the success for WP4 implementation and FORWARD in general. Therefore, this proposal will be taking into consideration the different levels of maturity of the OR's, namely the need to acknowledge the different levels of expertise as well as the objectives that should be linked to the situation of each OR's R&I ecosystem.

OR's R&I Officers level of expertise

The first step to create a capacity action plan is to define the level of need, therefore in order to turn knowledge from training into skills, it is important to have OR R&I officers of different levels of expertise and link Capacity actions for OR R&I officers to clear objectives for R&I communities.

It is relevant to define and organize the R&I Officers' group according to at least 4 levels of expertise, regarding the knowledge and capacities to support Researchers & Innovators in Competitive funding access. As the following:

Figure1. Levels of capacity and skills for OR Officers

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Having as base the analysis and conclusions of the WP2 reports and analysis we can understand that it is fundamental that any approach to the EU OR's should take into account the different levels of involvement and expertise of the 9 OR's R&I ecosystem. As the most evident example of that discrepancy, we have the Canary Island and Mayotte. Canary Islands were labeled by the WP2 leader, in the Mutual learning event conclusions, as a normal performer, since it's in the 140 position of a ranking of 274 FP participants regions, with 41 360 710, 00 euros of EU financing, a long distance reality of a non performer region as Mayotte. This region has a rating position of 271 and a total of 294 646,00 euros in EU financing from FP projects. The conclusions of the WP2 leader that has to frame the follow up of the WP4 strategy is that we need a tailor-made approach for each OR region; each profile requires a singular strategy; Horizon 2020/Europe is both a symptom of and a lever for the development of knowledge economy. This was in fact the strategy already presented in the D4.2 of the Common Capacity Plan with the needed adjustments to the 9 OR's realities and it will be the same strategy for the Common training programme for OR's R&I officers.

Target areas of capacity for OR's R&I Officers

In the common capacity actions presented in the D4.2 included in every Regional Capacity Plan, we identify the focus on the promotion of the R&I actor's capacities to monitoring and identifying calls, identify project partners to build consortiums, submit, develop and manage FP projects, even if in different levels of approach. In this regard this thematic is further explored in common target the OR Officers, within the D4.3 with focus in building a common Common training programme for OR's R&I officers.

The capacities for OR's Officers must include all the skills necessary during the lifetime of the project, from the capacity to identify calls, to the soft skills in networking necessary to build a consortium, as well as capacity to write a winning proposal, to have the abilities to manage successfully the project up to it's closing point, that implies skills that are more transversal and specific, as financial management, time managing, etc.

Figure 2. Project Life Cycle: the different stages

The Capacity Plans presented in the D4.1 report and in D4.2 report submitted in M9 and M22, respectively, to the European Commission, already previews capacity actions that target the skills needed in this different stages of the life cycle of a project. Those capacity actions can be identified equally in the capacity actions that have the OR’s R&I Officers as target, providing the training in the several stages needed to have a successful participation in FP projects and in EU financed projects in general. In order to analyze in more detail the capacities that the different OR selected for OR’s R&I Officers we have used the same table of qualification we have used in D4.2 to classify the skills and capacities for the target actors, in this case with focus on the OR’s R&I Officers (table 3).

As already referred in the report D4.2, “Common training programme for OR’s R&I actors”⁴, we identified the areas of choice by having as a starting point the main capacity skills to attain in order to have a more prepared and informed actors in the OR’S R&I ecosystems. Firstly the “FORWARD skills” is classified by the ground base capacities for increasing the FP participation of the R&I actors in OR’s that included capacities as identification of calls, successful proposals and managing funds, as well as communicating science and other capacities that are linked to FW actions and main target; the “EU funding” area is

⁴ submitted to the European Commission in the M22 of the FW project, October 2020

focused on the base, with overall awareness and knowledge of the R&I funding that exists in the EU and can be accessed better by the OR's R&I actors (FP; thematic calls and programs; EU networks, like ERA, RIS3 and Regional development, etc), in which the Framework Programs are included; the final area is the "Human Resources" capacities, as a transversal knowledge that allows the R&I actors to have skills that elevate the quality and capacity of the R&I actors, with focus on FP participation, as promoting a different conscience (entrepreneurship), concrete knowledge (financial skills), soft skills and other HR skills.

FORWARD - Target areas for capacity building		
Forward skills	EU Funding	Human Resources capacities
Management in Innovation	H2020 / Horizon Europe	Financial management
Project Manager	LIFE + and BEST	Training in specific areas – based on the WP3 areas
Identification of calls, successful proposals and managing funds	European funds regionally managed (FSE, FEDER, INTERREG B, etc.)	Development of soft skills (network building; team management; time; managing)
Communicating science	Call for Tenders - UE	Coaching in science
Stakeholders engagement strategy	Others EU funds managed by the EC (Maritime funds, INTERREG EUROPE, MAES, etc.)	Entrepreneurship
Knowledge transfer	Deep knowledge and alignment on EU networks, like ERA, RIS3 and Regional development	Writing impact sections

Table 3. Target areas for capacity building based on the FORWARD D4.2 report

By extracting and analyzing the information extracted from the Capacity building Proposal per OR, with the focus on the Capacity actions focused on the OR's R&I Officers (Annex 3⁵) we can analyze the common traits and trends in this capacitation process carried by FORWARD partners, dedicated to these actors from the R&I ecosystem. As a result of this analysis we can realize that in graphic 4 that the target areas

⁵ Tables provided by each OR WP4 Regional coordinator, with information extracted from each FW partners Capacity Action Plan in their region (some also updated, as in annex 3)with activities dedicated, or that includes, OR's R&I Officers

of capacity building for OR's R&I Officers are divided mainly between two areas: Human resources capacities, with 44 capacity actions, and EU Funding, and with 43 capacity actions on Human resources capacities.

Graphic 4. Information extracted from OR's FW Capacity Plan and divided into areas (table 3) that target's OR's R&I Officers

In terms of the number of capacity actions carried per OR for OR's R&I Officers we can verify in graphic 5 that there is a big disparity between the Canary Island offer and the other OR's. This can be explained by the maturity and size of the Canary island R&I ecosystem and critical mass, as also with the higher number of FW Partners in the consortium. Canary Islands leads the number of capacity actions, with the impressive 72 capacity actions (that are focus in OR Officers and others that also include these actors), when all the other OR's offer less than two digits training/capacity actions. With Azores (6), Madeira (6) and French Guiana (7) with the higher number of capacity actions/trainings.

Graphic 5. The OR's FW Capacity activities carried by FW partners for OR's R&I Officers

Graphic 6. Capacity training activities from FW partners, per OR, in the "Forward skills" target area (based on table 3 of target area qualification – D4.2 report) for OR R&I Officers

If we analyze the distribution per OR in the target areas of capacity building (as in table 3) we can conclude that the "FORWARD Skills" target area, being the less expressive in total, is very influenced by the low number of capacity numbers from Canary Islands, with 8 capacity actions in a total of 72 training actions. Canary Islands dedicated to the OR R&I Officers the least capacity actions in this category, however it leads the other OR's in terms of number of capacity actions in this target area, only followed by 4 training actions in this target area by French Guiana, Azores (3) and Mayotte (3).

Following an ascendant line of total number of capacity activities per target area for OR's R&I Officers we have the target area of "EU Funding" in which Canary islands has concentrated more capacity actions. In

this area we find the biggest difference between Canary Islands' number of actions and other OR's of the project, with just Madeira with 3 capacity actions in this target area.

Graphic 7. Capacity training activities from FW partners, per OR, in the “EU Funding” target area (based on table 3 of target area qualification – D4.2 report) for OR R&I Officers

In third place we have the “Human resources” area, with again another high number from Canary Islands in this category, with 31 training actions, followed again by Madeira 4 capacity actions in the context of this target area, as illustrated in the graphic number 8.

Graphic 8. Capacity training activities from FW partners, per OR, in the “Human Resources capacities” target area (based on table 3 of target area qualification – D4.2 report) for OR R&I Officers

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Finally we can also analyze another point related to training activities from the FW partners, per OR, dedicated/including the OR’s R&I Officers: the amount of capacity actions that are previewed within the FORWARD’s GA and the training that are outside this financial package. This last can be of different origins, either resourcing to internal budget to by using other projects and capacity actions that are free of cost at a regional, national (NCP, for example) or at an European and international level (provided by the EU programmed training events, free of charges).

	AZ	CA	GUA	GUY	MAD	MAR	MAY	REU	ST.M	TOTAL
In FW GA	6	20	5	6	1	3	2	5	2	50
Not previewed in FW GA	0	52	0	0	6	0	2	0	0	60
TOTAL	6	72	5	6	7	3	4	5	2	110

Table 4. Analysis of the number of capacity actions in FW that include OR’s R&I Officers according to the GA, as financed actions by the Forward project, and the ones that are financed outside Forward’s project.

Following the WP2 diagnostic of the OR’s R&I ecosystem the conclusion was that due to the different maturity and characteristics of the OR’s R&I regional community there was a need to create a Capacity Plan that adjusted to the regional reality.

WP4 Operationally

Reinforcing what was already mentioned in the context of the D4.1 and D4.2 report, the WP4, as a Capacity Building FORWARD Work Package, is engaged in following the new trends on online learning skills, having the present and future needs regarding the current constraints of the international health pandemic. There are still more questions on the effectivity of the process of engaging and networking, that can be an additional advantage to these activities, that could be an added value to the capacitation, specially between OR’s R&I Officers, not only within the Region and country, as well as the 9 OR’s level. The Capacity buildings plan has resources for digital methods to be implemented, as **e-Learning, web-seminars and podcasts**. However it also has another side of the coin, limiting the personal contact and the informal network that is not substituted by digital tools.

The platforms to be used to implement the actions is the choice and the responsibility of each FW partner, resourcing to already used digital platforms in their organization or if needed include any cost

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of utilization of these platform in the WP4 budget, keeping the costs within the previewed budget for these actions in the project budget, as previously previewed in D4.2.

Synergies with WP's

WP3

Regarding the contribution to “D4.3 Common training programme for OR's R&I officers” from WP3 leader (ITC, Canary Islands & Synergile, Guadalupe) perspective, these were some of the shared ideas.

Among the several tasks of the WP3, the co-creation of the thematic Action Plans is an important source of information for the training of the ORs R&I Officers. The Action Plans are prepared in respect of the Quadruple Helices innovation concept allowing to have a diverse public from University, Research Centre, SME, civil society and local government. The distribution of the ORs during these meetings (started in January 2021) is not fully balance put allows the presence of at least one person of seven on the nine ORs (i.e., Mayotte and Saint Martin due to their R&I low development cannot be represented in each of the eight TWG). Those thematic working Groups with a varied public but with common goals bring up personal and group experiences in research and innovation particularly in the context of fundraising, answer to call and management of funded projects.

Analysis of the Action Plan of the WP3, through the analysis report (D3.2 which will be available at the end of March 2021) will complete the WP2 mapping. Indeed, the possibility to join the main actors of the R&I by thematic will not only give information on R&I in the nine ORs in a quantitative way. The number of projects funded or the amounts received during the two last EU Framework Programme do not explain how they reach the bar of excellence and succeed to one or several calls. According to WP3 leader the point of view, the experience, the disappointment and the hope of the actors are visible in the specific objectives theirs proposes and the support their request in training and human resource.

The WP4 and WP3 can join efforts to support WP4 results with an internal survey in coordination with the Thematic Working Groups, in order to inquire the relevance and future needs of the network OR's R&I Officers network. The questionnaire should identify the answers per region, and address questions to the Members related to the support they already have from their regional network, as well as rate of success from those that received support. Also we can have a better notion of the OR's that provide in fact this support and the ones that don't or that don't do it effectively, as well as the needs that these end users

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(researchers) request from the OR's R&I Officers. Since at this stage the TWG are still starting their works, focuses on co-creating their action plans, this exercise will be done after the TWG are up and running in a context of an Action Plan.

The outcomes of the WP3, foreseen in the Forward GA, i.e. the eight thematic Action Plans, and all activities around their implementation will help to have another mapping of the actors of the R&I of the ORs, not at the scale of the organizations but at human scale. Despite the fact that those projects are led by a private or public structure, the role of the leaders is essential. This is proved by the development of the MCSA which pushes to better support the future leaders in R&I allowing them to raise their international experience and skills.

The training of the ORs' R&I Officers will take the support of the results of the WP3 but also exchange (i.e., video of the workshops) to have a better representation of the future actors of Horizon Europe, their strength, their weakness and their potential evolution.

Regarding the Tasks the WP3 vision is:

Task 4.3 Establishment of a network of dedicated OR R&I Officers

- From WP3 perspective: TWGs will be the customers of the network of OR R&I Officers. Once the TWGs have defined their action plans, OR R&I Officers can be requested to support TWGs needs. In that way we can test our hypothesis on the network services and if it fits with the expectations of the researchers / innovators;
- Other ideas: After the R&D mapping on WP2, it was identified the existing EU project offices in Universities and other research organizations. These experts can act as mentors of newcomers, and use WP5 networking activities for study visits (onsite or virtual).

Task 4.4 Capacity Building for OR's Officers

- From WP3 perspective and focusing on Horizon Europe: Provide OR Officers specific training/knowledge on the thematic of the working groups (Pillar 2, clusters aligned with the thematic). It can be possible that each OR specializes in a thematic (the most relevant to the OR) and the knowledge is shared among the network;
- Put attention on widening programme and opportunities for ORs;
- The training / info days for OR officers could be organized through the NCPs for all ORs;

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- Once the OR's Officers are trained, they can organize webinars for the TWGs on Horizon Europe opportunities.

WP5

According to *Agencia Canaria de Investigación, Innovación y Sociedad de la información*, as WP5 leader, the actions to be implemented within WP5 might be useful also for WP4, particular for Tasks 4.2 *Capacity building and supporting activities for R&I actors*, where activities such as knowledge exchange and cooperation activities, including training, seminars, webinars, MOOCs/online courses, and/or summer school activities were programmed. Additionally, for Task 4.3. *Establishment of a network of dedicated OR R&I Officers* the WP4 could benefit directly from the WP5 activities, with the participation of these R&I Officers in activities foreseen in Action 5.1 *Organisation of and participation of networking and brokerage events*, particularly in Action 5.1.1 *Organization scientific conferences* or Action 5.1.2 *Organization of other tailored events* (workshops, brokerage events, etc.) where these Officers could support the R&I actors from their regions in order to improve networking and promote new consortiums and proposal preparation. These activities could contribute to the implementation of the Task 4.4 *Capacity Building for OR's Officers* since they should utilize their new skills and knowledge gain in the theoretically capacity actions on real situation.

Also OR R&I Officers could provide support to R&I actors, in those actions foreseen in Task 5.2 *Organization of short-term oriented networking activities* and Task 5.3 *Organization of long-term oriented networking activities* promoting the knowledge transfer and strengthen the network between OR's Officers.

WP6

This WP led by ARDITI, Madeira, and dedicated to building bridges between researchers and political decision makers the position shared related to the synergies that can come out of the combination of efforts between WP4 and WP6 is divided in two levels: political and technical.

At the political level:

- Facilitating the dialogue between the research community and policy makers; Contribute to further development and implementation of Smart Specialization Strategies (S3/RIS3), and contribute to more tailored EU policies for ORs and fine-tuned programming of regional policies for each OR;

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- The need to consider a long-term perspective => research policy can't be bounded by 4-5 year electoral cycles => the need for the agreement on the implementation and continued support of long-term sustainability plans and measures in R&I which go beyond electoral cycles;
- Underdeveloped Research structures in OR => present recommendations / R&I project proposals, which can strengthen research ecosystems in outermost regions.

At a technical level:

The WP6 and the T4.3 is linked by the T6.2 (Recommendations for future EU policies on OR's) and T6.3 (Ensuring sustainability of long-term research activities in ORs).

T6.2 - Recommendations for future EU policies on OR's

- An action line (ii) «Designing a common strategy for institutional cooperation & common governance in OR's regarding Research and Innovation topics»

Taking as a reference/baseline the work carried and the results of projects RIS3_Net1 (concluded) and RIS3_Net2 (started in 2020) in the MAC regions (Madeira-Azores-Canarias), FORWARD partners will extend / adapt it, designing a common strategy for institutional cooperation & common governance in OR's.

- An action line (ii) for cooperation in the scope of OR R&I Officers is an intrinsic part of T6.2 action;
- An action line (iii) «Enabling OR participation in broader consortia & agreements».

The aim of this activity is to seek/foster cooperation in R&D with third countries, to be linked / combined with WP4 (Capacity building) and WP5 (Networking activities) and contributing to the development of EU policies regarding the OR's. Following action line (ii) this activity may / should also add an external dimension to a potential / future OR's RIS3.

The T6.3 - Ensuring sustainability of long-term research activities in OR's - interconnects with task 3.3 (Thematic action plans); 3.4 (Sustainability solutions for thematic working groups); 4.4 (Capacity Building for OR's Officers) and 4.5 (Operational and sustainability Strategy for OR's Officers). Efforts must be made in order to organize the results of these tasks that will help to support the long-term sustainability plan, including technical meetings with WP & Task leaders in order to find common solutions and avoid unnecessary duplication of work.

Multi-WP Synergies

In order to promote the synergies of WP's in order to benefit the OR's R&I Officers, we suggest to organize a Workshop to the OR's R&I Officers focused on their knowledge regarding the stage of the R&I ecosystem in OR's. It is essential that the OR's Officers benefit from networking activities and be aware of the situation of the R&I communities, at thematic level, in a way that they have an in-depth transversal snapshot. Therefore, as soon as the Thematic Action Plans are ready (end of February 2020) in the WP3 Thematic Working Groups we should advance in coordination with the WPL, of WP5 and WP4 and WP3, the organization of a Webinar dedicated to the OR's R&I Officers. This way the OR's R&I Officers are aware of the thematic state and strategy vision, as an WP3 and WP4 activity, and offer them the opportunity to be trained/knowledge sharing by the Coordinators from each TWG on the Action Plans per thematic. This initiative allows also an opportunity to contact with their peers in the other OR allowing WP5 actions to take place, by facilitating networking.

OPERATIONAL WORK PLAN

The present situation has limited the actions of the WP5 (networking actions) and as limited actions of the WP6 (bridging the decision makers and researchers), as well as it obliged the OR's to rethink the way they will implement their capacity actions, being restricted in most cases to online activities. This situation may demand a better alignment between regions and within the region between the actors in order to ensure the productive implementation and the desired outcomes of the actions.

The digital platforms allow to keep the activities going on despite the constraints; it also allows the regions to promote synergies and allow participation of other regions in their capacity actions, although the digital tool does not substitute human contact/proximity.

The FW partners are keeping a close watch on the development of the situation in 2020 as well in 2021 in order to adjust actions and define the way the fellowships and other synergies actions from other WP's to be implemented. Due to this situation, many FW partners have postponed the implementation of capacity actions to 2021 that will concentrate actions during a period that is closer to the first call to be launched in the context of Horizon Europe.

Implemented actions

- Presentation of the WP4 roadmap during the Kick off meeting to the GA partners, February 2019 in Las Palmas, Canary Islands;
- Presentation of a draft proposal to partners on WP4 during a GA meeting online – on the 19th of June 2019- 10h30 Azores time/ 12h30 Brussels time;
- Mutual learning event, 8-9-10 October 2019, Canary Islands Brussels Office, Avenue Livingstone 21, Brussels – creation of a Joint Strategy for OR's R&I ecosystem in the context of FORWARD project
- A Workshop session with FORWARD SC partners on WP4 Capacity Plan (M7) during the meeting in Reunion Island – France;
- A regional meetings with the FW partners and eventual R&I key partners, identified in the WP2;
- A Regional Coordinator was appointed in representation of the WP4 in their respective OR's in the 14th of May 2020;
- Presentation of the WP4 progress and roadmap in the WP3 Subcoordinators kick off (17th of September);
- Meeting with the Regional Coordinators to present possible opportunities of synergies in capacity and training activities between regional partners in the FW project (15th October 2020) and analyze the development of the D4.2 report;
- ✓ Present the WP4 evolution to the Advisory Members in the FORWARD online meeting of the 22th October – challenge them to volunteer to lead capacity talks to the FW partners;
- ✓ Present the WP4 evolution to the Advisory Members in the FORWARD online meeting of the 22th October – challenge them to volunteer to lead capacity talks to the FW partners;
- ✓ Presentation the WP4 updates on the D4.3 report on the Steering Committee of the 14th January 2021.

Planned short/medium term actions

- Implementation of referred capacitation activities by FW partners in their OR's, based on the activities foreseen in Annex 3 from D4.1;
- Punctual meetings, as well one-to-one meetings (when required) with the Regional Coordinators for WP4;
- Close contact per Regional Coordinators with the Sub-ordinators of the WP3 Thematic Working Groups in order to follow up the engagement and information regarding Forward project capacitation actions;
- Continuous communication with other WPS, namely WP2, WP5, WP6 and WP8 leaders, in further synergies and promotion of common goals in the FW project, as well as sharing the challenges and solutions due to the current situation of pandemic;
- Receive inputs from the WP4 RC regarding the results of the implementation of the Regional Capacity Plans and multi-regional synergies;
- Organize with the WP5 and WP3 a joint Knowledge Sharing/Training from the TWG Coordinators to the OR's R&I Officers, on the previewed Thematic Action Plans;
- Prepare with the WP3 leader a questionnaire to be presented to the Thematic Working Groups and request information regarding the relevance and impact of the OR's R&I network.

CONCLUSIONS

The OR's R&I Officers existence depends on the political dimension at 3 levels - the awareness, priorities and financial availability. Based on the consultations, this report allowed the OR's to demonstrate the need and the relevance role of the Regional Contact Points figure. This report intends that the FORWARD output provides scientific and expertise based information to implement the OR's Officer networks in order to promote the OR's participation in the European R&I Financing Programmes.

Despite the COVID situation, that has constrained not only the construction of this report, as well as the development and implementation of the activities of the FORWARD project, as it happened in other H2020 projects, the OR's were able to adapt and still deliver. This situation allowed us all, as OR's the opportunity to rethink other ways to connect and work on OR's network by using digital tools. The advantages of the digital tools are undeniable, namely to overcome geographical constraints as Outermost Regions, and should be taken on to account in to implement actions, namely capacity actions. However the digital option should be balanced with in-person events as these are more inclusive, as well as it allows another level of engagement at a personal level that benefits learning and more personal and engaging relationships, fundamental to create consortiums and joint projects, for example.

Having already the "lesson learned" from the WP2 diagnose, where we concluded that the level of maturity of the OR's due to its very different conditions, at a geographical, political, FP involvement, etc , have at a very different starting point it is relevant to analyze, define and organize the R&I Officers according to the OR's needs and present level of development reached. Its important to have a common focus in terms of goals and provide training and capacity actions in the several stages of a project life cycle, needed to have a successful participation in FP projects and in EU financed projects in general, however it should also provide a Capacity Plan that corresponds to the needs of the different levels of expertise, regarding the knowledge and capacities to support Researchers & Innovators in Competitive funding access.

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The existence of dedicated services providing assistance dedicated to FP support and other R&I financing in the EU to local stakeholders, including project development, management and reporting, is an asset to increase regional participation in EU financed programmes and promote the development of regional research and innovation and in all regions is lacking still capacitation.

The combination of the capacity buildings activities, adjusted to needs of the local R&I actors, as well as network of OR's R&I Officers, for dissemination and awareness of the Framework Programmes, supporting on the identification, submission and follow up of their financed EU projects in R&I, will have a fundamental impact on the success of the FORWARD goals and on the OR's R&I community development toward a higher participation in the FP Programmes.

Forward project has launched an ambition joint plan for OR's R&I network and the Capacity Plans allow not only new and improved skills for more a competitive R&I community, as also a change in mind-set regarding innovation and science in Europe. As European Commission stated, a "shared agenda between regions, Member States and the European Commission is essential [...] so that Europe becomes a true global leader in innovation for all"⁶. The establishment of a formal OR's Officers networks will allow that all OR's gain more together than apart, as they have complementary infrastructures for excellence in science, expertise's, network connections, namely with Third countries, and it helps to reinforce the existence of a more informed and trained R&I community in the OR's, a reinforced critical mass in the different scientific thematic areas.

By reinforcing the OR's Officers capacities and access to support Forward project benefits the promoting of the excellence in science in the OR's, as well as it strengthens the position of the OR's in the EU, contributing to a more cohesive and inclusive European Union. The OR's should go beyond the mindset of "outermostness" in to an affirmation of its singularity, as R&I added value for the EU, that contributes for the Union leadership in R&I at a global scale.

⁶ A renewed European Agenda for Research and Innovation - Europe's chance to shape its future, The European Commission's contribution to the Informal EU Leaders' meeting on innovation in Sofia on 16 May 2018 (Brussels, 15.5.2018 COM(2018) 306 final), p. 19.

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- IX. *Common technical position of the OR S3 Network regarding Component 5 – Interregional innovation investments*, March 31st of 2017, the Presidents of the Outermost Regions (ORs)
- X. *Report from FORWARD project (824550), Work Package 4 - D4.1 Capacity building plan Report*, July 2020
- XI. *Report from FORWARD project (824550), Work Package 4 - D4.2 Common training programme for OR's R&I actors*, October 2020

ANNEX 1: Power Point of the WP4 Technical meeting for the D4.3 (WP4) Regional Coordinators

WP4 Technical meeting meeting
09th December 2020

Deliverable 4.3 - Common training programme for OR's R&I officers

WP4 leader: FRCT

GOVERNO DOS AÇORES

FRCT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550.

Deliverables on WP4

Deliverable Number	Deliverable title	Type	Dissemination level	Due date
D4.1	Capacity building plan	Report	Public	M18-M19*
D4.2	Common training programme for OR's R&I actors	Report	Public	M18-M22*
D4.3	Common training programme for OR's R&I officers	Report	Public	M25
D4.4	OR R&I Offices Operational and Sustainability Strategic for implementation	Report	Public	M36

*Suffered delay due to COVID context

GA

Deliverable 4.3 - Common training programme for OR's R&I officers

GOAL: "A common training programme for ORs' R&I officers will be developed to provide a **common basis for the training of ORs' Officer teams to develop the services expected from the ORs' Officers.**"

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550.

GA

Task 4.4 Capacity Building for OR's Officers – Objectives for D4.3

Provide the OR's Officers teams the necessary training to develop the services expected from the OR's Officers:

- ✓ Understanding the specificities of their R&I ecosystems to provide a customise guidance on choosing relevant H2020 topics and types of action;
- ✓ Advice on administrative procedures and contractual issues;
- ✓ Training and assistance on proposal writing;
- ✓ Distribution of documentation (forms, guidelines, manuals etc.);
- ✓ Assistance in partner search promoting international networking activities and collaborations.

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- ### Co-creation process – D4.3 questions
1. What is the role of an OR’s Officer?
 2. Why OR’s Officer are important for the implementation of FORWARD goals and legacy?
 3. Why capacitation for OR’s Officer can make a difference?
 4. What are the base capacities/skills for OR’s Officers?
 5. In which organizations our OR’S Officers should be integrated?
 6. How many OR Officer’s should we have in our Region(s)?
 7. Which thematic priorities should the OR Officers target in the Regional & Innovation ecosystem?
-
This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550.

Questions on OR's R&I Officers

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Contacts of the NCP's

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Co-creation process for D4.3

Deadline: 22th of December

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 824550.

Calendar of next steps for D4.3

- ✓ **From 23th of november to 2th of December** : fill in with the extracted info from Annex 3, Regional Capacity Plan, with the focus of the R&I Officers – no REPLY – extended to 04th of December
- ✓ **From 4th to 15th December**: send a list of co-construction questions to request the reply from OR's Government and at the NCP level (coordinated with SC members and Regional Coordinator for WP4)/ Fill in table with National Contact contacts;
- ✓ **9th or 10th December**: Technical meeting with Regional Coordinator for WP4 – to introduce the work and Q&A;
- ✓ **From 15th to 22th December**: Technical meeting with the Regional Coordinators & WP leaders (WP3; WP8; WP6) for the co-construction – receive replies from the questions at a regional and national level;
- ✓ **From 4th to 6th January** : Make the report available for inputs/comments in the FW google drive;
- ✓ **7th to the 8th January 2021**: Integrate the inputs and comments on the final document;
- ✓ **From 11 -15th January 2021**: Make it available for voting remotely (if you agree this may be the best process) by doodle for the Steering Committee members;
- ✓ **17th January**: D4.2 Report is submitted to the EC

Note: deadline for submission is the 31th of January

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For any further questions or support please contact the WP4 leader (FRCT)

Thank you

Lina Silveira
FRCT Project manager for FORWARD

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ANNEX 2: Questions directed to the NCP and the OR'S R&I Regional political structures

Questions

1. What is the role of an OR's R&I Officer?
2. Why OR's R&I Officer are important for the implementation of FORWARD goals and legacy?
3. Why capacitation for OR's R&I Officer can make a difference?
4. What are the base capacities/skills for OR's R&I Officers?
5. In which organizations our OR's R&I Officers should be integrated?
6. How many OR R&I Officer's should we have in our Region(s)?
7. Which thematic priorities should the OR R&I Officers target in the Regional & Innovation ecosystem?

ANNEX 3: Tables of Capacity actions for OR's R&I Officers per OR

Azores

Outermost Region: Azores						
Name of the WP4 Regional Coordinator: Lina Silveira						
FW partner	Type of capacity action	In the context of the FW GA (Yes/No)	Implemented? (Yes/No)	Name/title of the Capacity action	Specific for OR's Officer (or also for other actors in R&I ecosystem)?	Key words - Goal & Skills to be attained
FRCT	Advanced Training Skills - Fellowship	YES	NO	EU network, access to calls	OR Officers	Networking skills, identification of calls
FRCT	Advanced Training Skills - Fellowship	YES	NO	Training for Trainer in FP	OR Officers	Promoting new habits to increase their connection capacities; identify calls; how to write impactful proposals; key factors for managing a EU projects. Know their ecosystem to link it to opportunities
FRCT	Advanced Training Skills - Fellowship	YES	NO	Brussels Training in the EU	OR Officers	Get information on the field on the needed skills to access the right networks and know better the requirements and reality of the EU strategy and way of work of the EU institutions
UAc	Online training	YES	YES	Financial rules of H2020 and Horizon Europe	Project Manager - potential OR Officers	Training of project managers: participation in FP / Optimizing financial excellence / Knowledge of new forms of cost "Lump Sump"
UAc	Online training	YES	YES	HORIZON EUROPE: 2021-2027	Project Manager - potential OR Officers	Ensure know-how to participate in future FP and increase the number of proposals / Increase regional knowledge about specific calls, among other aspects

Delivreable 4.3 - Common training programme for OR's R&I officers

Outermost Region: Canary Islands

Name of the WP4 Regional Coordinator: ULPGC/FCPCT

FW partner	Type of capacity action	In the context of the FW GA (Yes/No)	Implemented? (Yes/No)	Name/title of the Capacity action	Specific for OR's Officer (or also for other actors in R&I ecosystem)?	Key words - Goal & Skills to be attained
ULL/ULPGC/FCPCT	[Workshops for R&I actors]	Yes	Expected by 14/01/2021	R&D collaborative projects (HE)	YES (1) Researchers from FW-CAN partners 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners 3) enterprises	[EU funding] HE at first glance (Missions, RIAs, IA, CSA...)
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Workshops for R&I actors] Training 2: Webinar organised by FW partner	Yes	No. (Q2) 2021	Writing successful EU R&I proposals	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners 3) SMEs (CEO, EU Project Managers 4) Tecnologos funded by ACISI	[Soft skills] successful proposals
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Infoday] organised by FW partner	No	No. (Q3) 2021	TBD	YES. All	[EU funding] TBD specific area/Programme (pillar I, II or III)
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	BBI-JU infoday EC_220420_online	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] BBI-JU call

ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinario MSCA-IF_280420	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] MSCA-IF Call
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	MSCA: Webinario MSCA IF 2020: ¿Cómo escribir una propuesta competitiva?_06/05/20	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] MSCA-IF successful proposals
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinar ERC-ADG_cómo preparar propuestas_190520	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] ERC-ADG successful proposals I
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinario MSCA-COFUND-2020_280520	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] MSCA COFUND call
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinar: cómo preparar ERC_ADG_2020 exitosa (parte II)_290520	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] ERC-ADG successful proposals II
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q3) 2020	Webinario Implementación HE_RedOE_160720	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] HE at first glance (Missions, RIAs, IA, CSA...)
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q3) 2020	Jornada inform CDTI_EU Green Deal_011020	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] EU GREEN DEAL call
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	CDTI_Jornada presentacion HE España_02/031220	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] HE at first glance (Missions, RIAs, IA, CSA...)
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinar ERC-ADG_cómo preparar propuestas_190520	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] ERC-ADG successful proposals I
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinario MSCA-COFUND-2020_280520	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] MSCA COFUND call
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinar: cómo preparar ERC_ADG_2020 exitosa (parte II)_290520	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] ERC-ADG successful proposals II

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ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q3) 2020	Webinario Implementación HE_RedOE_160720	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] HE at first glance (Missions, RIAs, IA, CSA...)
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q3) 2020	Jornada inform CDTI_EU Green Deal_011020	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] EU GREEN DEAL call
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	CDTI_ Jornada presentacion HE España_02/031220	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] HE at first glance (Missions, RIAs, IA, CSA...)
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	CDTI_ Jornada presentacion HE España_02/031220	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] HE at first glance (Missions, RIAs, IA, CSA...)
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	No. (Q4) 2020	ERC_Taller II: StG+CoG 2021 - 16 Diciembre	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] ERC-STG/COG successful proposals I
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	No. (Q4) 2020	ERC_Taller III Aprendiendo de ERC-Starting Grant 2020_17 diciembre 20	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] ERC-STG/COG successful proposals II
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	No. (Q4) 2020	Infoday MSCA call on HE_111220	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[EU funding] MSCA call HE
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by consultants	No	Yes. (Q1) 2020	EMDESK The essentials of running a H2020 project_250220	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] leadership
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by consultants	No	Yes. (Q1) 2020	EMDESK Preparing RP_190220	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Finance] Reporting Periods
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by consultants	No	Yes. (Q1) 2020	EMDESK_Remote EU Project Manag_310320	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] leadership
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by consultants	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	EMDESK_Webinar: EM Guidelines for data management_280520	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] DMP

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ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by consultants	No	Yes. (Q3) 2020	EMDESK_Avoiding financial mismanagement and getting ready for a CFS and audits_170920	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Finance] CFS and audits
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by consultants	No	Yes. (Q3) 2020	EMDESK_5 steps to take when you've received a Horizon 2020 grant_291020	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Finance] Avoiding financial errors
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by EC Services	No	Yes. (Q3) 2020	IPR HELPDESK_Why researchers need an IP strategy_081020	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] IPR
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Webinario] Online free registration events organised by EC Services	No	Yes. (Q3) 2020	IPR HELPDESK_IP in EU-funded Projects/Horizon 2020_141020	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from FCPCT	[Soft skills] IPR
ULPGC/FCPCT	[Workshops for R&I actors] organised by FW partner (ITC)	Yes	Yes. (Q4) 2020	HYPERION_Sean_ITC_EEN_031220	YES, all	[EU funding] HE
IAC	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 1: Webinar organised by FW partner	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	Webinar about the Widening Program in HE 23/11/20	1) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	[EU funding] WIDENING Call
IAC	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 1: Webinar organised by FW partner	Yes	No. (Q2) 2021	Webinar about the European Research Council (ERC)	1) Researchers from FW-CAN partners 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	
IAC	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 1: Webinar organised by FW partner	Yes	No. (Q3) 2021	Technical Management and Economics of HORIZON EUROPE Projects	All	[Finance] Reporting Periods and audits
IAC	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	CDTI_Jornada presentacion HE España_02/031220	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from IAC	[EU funding] HE at first glance (Missions, RIAs, IA, CSA...)
IAC	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	No. (Q4) 2020	Researcher Career & MSCA in the next framework programme 11/12/20	Researchers (postdoc/senior)	[EU funding] MSCA call
IAC	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 1:	No	No. (Q2) 2021	Webinar MSCA	Researchers (postdoc/senior)	[EU funding] MSCA call

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	Webinar organised by FW partner					
IAC	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 1: Webinar organised by FW partner	No	No. (Q3) 2021	How to write a competitive proposal.	Researchers (postdoc/senior)	[Soft skills] HE successful proposals
IAC	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 1: Webinar organised by FW partner	No	No. (Q4) 2021	Open collaboration with companies	All	[Soft skills] Networking & IPR
PLOCAN	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	CDTI_ Jornada presentacion HE España_02/031220	YES. 1) EU Project Managers from PLOCAN	[EU funding] HE at first glance (Missions, RIAs, IA, CSA...)
PLOCAN	[Training for clusters and companies] Training 1: Online organized by PLOCAN	Yes	No. (Q1) 2021	European funding 2021-2027: R&I enterprise projects (for high TRLs)	Yes, but focused on 1) SMEs 2) Researchers 3) Technologists/ EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	[EU funding] Project and funding types, EITs and best practices
PLOCAN	[Training for clusters and companies] Training 2: Online organized by PLOCAN	Yes	No. (Q1) 2021	Writing successful EU R&I proposals	Yes, but focused on 1) SMEs 2) Researchers 3) Technologists/ EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	[Soft skills] successful proposals: HE vs H2020, proposal sections, partnerships, lessons learned and successful case
PLOCAN	[Training for clusters and companies] Training 3: Online organized by PLOCAN	Yes	No. (Q1) 2021	Development and management of European projects	Yes, but focused on 1) SMEs 2) Researchers 3) Technologists/ EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	[Soft skills] project management: What does it mean to win a European project?, types of partners, reports and timesheets, lessons learned, successful case
PLOCAN	[Workshops for R&I actors] organized by FW partner (ITC)	Yes	Yes. (Q4) 2020	HYPERION_Seau_ITC_EEN_031220	Yes, all	

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PLOCAN	[Fellowships to attend training abroad_1]	Yes		ERC: How to design a successful proposal - for Horizon Europe* (if possible)	1) Technologist PLOCAN / 2) EU Project Manager PLOCAN/ 3)Project managers from FW partners	
PLOCAN	[Fellowships to attend training abroad_2]	Yes		Management, coordination and implementation of coordinated projects – for Horizon Europe* (if possible)	1) Technologist PLOCAN / 2) EU Project Manager PLOCAN/ 3)Project managers from FW partners	
ACISI	[Trainings on Entrepreneurship] Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	Yes	Expected by Q2 2021	Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs) funding opportunities and proposal preparation	- SMEs (CEO) - SMEs (EU Project Managers) - EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners - Tecnólogos/Gestores de la Innovación - Clusters	
ACISI	[Trainings on Entrepreneurship] Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	Yes	Expected by Q2 2021	Proposal preparation to lever Interregional cooperation for SMES and Cluster	- SMEs (CEO) - SMEs (EU Project Managers) - EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners - Tecnólogos/Gestores de la Innovación - Clusters	
ULL	[Workshops for R&I actors] organised by ULL		Yes. (Q1) 2020	Getting ready for Horizon Europe + How to write the impact of a H2020 Proposal (Pillar II and III)	All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners 3) SMEs	EU Funding + soft skills
ULL	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 1: Webinar organised by FW partner	Yes	Expected by Q1 2021	Writing successful MSCA proposals	1) Researchers from FW-CAN partners 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	Soft skills

ULL	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 2: Webinar organised by FW partner	Yes	Expected by Q2 2021	Introduction to HE	All	EU Funding
ULL + ULPGC	[Workshops for R&I actors]	Yes	Expected by 14/01/2021	R&D collaborative projects (HE)	YES (1) Resarchers from FW-CAN partners 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners 3) enterprises	Soft skills
ULL	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 2: Webinar organised by FW partner	No	Yes. (Q3) 2020	Data Management Plans for EU Projects	YES. All	Soft skills
ULL	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 2: Webinar organised by FW partner	No	Yes. (Q3) 2021	IPR in EU projects	YES.All	Soft skills
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Expected by Q3 2021	to be defined: EU Green Deal, Clusters, Missions HE, etc..	YES. All	EU Funding
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinario Acciones Individuales MSCA IF 2020: aspectos generales relevantes_28042020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	EU Funding
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinario Acciones Individuales MSCA IF 2020: Aspectos prácticos_06052020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	Soft skills
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Charla con tu NCP: Sesiones para personal de gestión y supervisión IF de entidades españolas_13/200520	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	Soft skills

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ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinar: cómo preparar una propuesta Advanced Grant 2020 exitosa (parte I)_190520	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	Soft skills
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	Webinar: LIFE 2020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	EU funding
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q2) 2020	2º Taller on-line preparación propuestas convocatoria Advanced Grant 2020 + experiencia caso práctico_29052020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	Soft skills
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q1) 2020	Webinar Convocatorias WP2021 del European Research Council (ERC). Área sanitaria - entorno clínico_22102020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	Soft skills
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q1) 2020	Jornada Informativa Nacional – European Research Council_ convocatorias 2021_28102020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	Soft skills
ULL	[Webinar] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q3) 2020	Infoday: LIFE4BEST_14092020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	EU Funding
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	Jornada informativa Acciones Marie Skłodowska-Curie (MSCA) en Horizonte Europa_11122020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	EU Funding
ULL	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by BiodivERsA/WATER-JPI	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	Information webinar on the BiodivERsA/WATER-JPI joint call_27102020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	EU Funding
ULL	[Trainings/workshops for researchers] Training 1:	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	Webinar oportunidades para Canarias en Programa de Trabajo	YES. All, but priority EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	EU Funding

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	Webinar organised by FW partner			Widening - Horizonte Europa _23112020		
ULL	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	CDTI_ Jornada presentacion HE España_02/031220	YES. All	EU Funding
ULL	European IP Helpdesk	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	European IP Helpdesk - Follow up Email Impact and Innovation in Horizon 2020: a Guide for Proposers_24112020	YES. All	EU Funding
ULL	[Infoday] Online free registration events organised by CDTI/FECYT/CE	No	Yes. (Q1) 2020	Infoday: Pacto Verde Europeo (EU Green Deal)_01102020	YES. All	EU Funding
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	Taller I: StG+CoG 2021_15122020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	EU Funding + soft skills
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	Taller II: StG+CoG ERC 2021_16122020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	EU Funding + soft skills
ULL	[Trainings on scientific excellence] Infoday/webinario NCP organised by FECYT/MINECO	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	Taller III: Aprendiendo de Starting Grant 2020 PIs & panel members_17122020	YES. All, but priority 1) Researchers 2) EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners	EU Funding + soft skills
ITC	[Workshops for R&I actors] organised by ITC	No	Yes. (Q4) 2020	HYPERION_Sean_ITC_EEN_031220		
ITC	[Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation] Training 1: Webinar/Seminar/workshop (online or presential but organised from the FW-CAN partner. It can be presented by the partner or be subcontracted to a consultant).	Yes	Expected Q1 / Q2 2021	European funding 2021-2027: R&I enterprise projects	- SMEs (CEO) - SMEs (EU Project Managers) - EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners - Tecnólogos/Gestores de la Innovación - Clusters	

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ITC	[Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation] Training 2: Webinar/Seminar/workshop (online or presential but organised from the FW-CAN partner. It can be presented by the partner or be subcontracted to a consultant).	Yes	Expected Q3 / Q4 2021	Development and management of European projects	- SMEs (CEO) - SMEs (EU Project Managers) - EU Project Managers from FW-CAN partners - Tecnólogos/Gestores de la Innovación - Clusters
ITC	[Fellowships to attend training abroad_1]	Yes	tbc	INFO Day + Training	PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP; e.g. writing successful R&I proposals; how to find EU opportunities; Introduction to HE; Management and coordination of EC-funded projects
ITC	[Fellowships to attend training abroad_1]	Yes	tbc	INFO Day + Training	PROJECT MANAGERS FROM FW PARTNERS: Increase the participation in FP; e.g. writing successful R&I proposals; how to find EU opportunities; Introduction to HE; Management and coordination of EC-funded projects

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Delivreable 4.3 - Common training programme for OR's R&I officers

Outermost Region: GUADELOUPE

Name of the WP4 Regional Coordinator: Sophie LARRIEU

FW partner	Type of capacity action	In the context of the FW GA (Yes/No)	Implemented? (Yes/No)	Name/title of the Capacity action	Specific for OR's Officer (or also for other actors in R&I ecosystem)?	Key words - Goal & Skills to be attained
REG GUA	Live Webinar	yes	No	Presentation of the H2020 program and specific programs	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Horizon Europe / Knowledge Give Information dedicated to H2020 and funding opportunities for French Guiana candidates to foster their participation in HORIZON funding programs
REG GUA	Live Webinar	yes	No	Essentials for success in European Research and Innovation Programmes	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Knowledge Collaboration Give the support services new competences in terms of coaching researchers in their proposal development effort and a precise methodology to develop winning proposals.
REG GUA	Trainings/workshops	yes	No	Project management and financial reporting of European Projects	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Horizon Europe / Give technical and administrative information on how to develop and manage H2020 proposals and projects.
REG GUA	Trainings/workshops	yes	No	Financial Aspects in H2020	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Horizon Europe / Give technical and administrative information on how to develop and manage the financial part of H2020 proposals and projects.
REG GUA	Training/workshop	yes	No	How to engage stakeholders to exploit successfully Horizon Europe programme	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Stakeholders engagement/Demystifying /Eligibility criterion/how to get feedback from experts/Connecting / R&I Coaching /Acting like champion

| |
|---|---|--|------------------------|---|--|--|---|
| Outermost Region: French Guiana | | | | | | | |
| Name of the WP4 Regional Coordinator: Laurent Linguet | | | | | | | |
| FW partner | Type of capacity action | In the context of the FW GA (Yes/No) | Implemented ? (Yes/No) | Name/title of the Capacity action | Specific for OR's Officer (or also for other actors in R&I ecosystem)? | Key words - Goal & Skills to be attained | |
| UG & CTG | Live Webinar | yes | No | Presentation of the H2020 program and specific programs | OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem | Horizon Europe / Knowledge Give Information dedicated to H2020 and funding opportunities for French Guiana candidates to foster their participation in HORIZON funding programs | |
| UG & CTG | Live Webinar | yes | No | Essentials for success in European Research and Innovation Programmes | OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem | Knowledge Collaboration Give the support services new competences in terms of coaching researchers in their proposal development effort and a precised methodology to develop winning proposals. | |
| UG & CTG | Trainings/workshops on project management and development | yes | No | Project management and financial reporting of European Projects | OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem | Horizon Europe / Give technical and administrative information on how to develop and manage H2020 proposals and projects. | |
| UG & CTG | Trainings/workshops on project management and development | yes | No | Financial Aspects in H2020 | OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem | Horizon Europe / Give technical and administrative information on how to develop | |

						and manage the financial part of H2020 proposals and projects.
UG & CTG	Training/workshop	yes	No	Training in productivity and time management	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Knowledge Collaboration Allow to learn organization techniques and prioritizing tasks
UG & CTG	Training/workshop	yes	No	Training on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Identify opportunities, develop business plans and capture the value created, Learn to collaborate effectively with other actors and specialists internal and external to your company or in specific ecosystems, How to grow your customer base through inbound and outbound marketing

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Reunion Island

Outermost Region: Reunion Island							
Name of the WP4 Regional Coordinator: Evelyne Tarnus							
FW partner	Type of capacity action	In the context of the FW GA (Yes/No)	Implemented? (Yes/No)	Name/title of the Capacity action	Specific for OR's Officer (or also for other actors in R&I ecosystem)?	Key words - Goal & Skills to be attained	
NEXA	Training/workshop	YES	YES	Coaching session: how to write a winning RISE/ITN proposal	YES	OR's officer	
NEXA	Live Webinar	YES	YES	Essentials for success in European Research and Innovation Programmes	YES	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	
NEXA	Training/workshop	YES	YES	How to engage stakeholders to exploit successfully Horizon Europe programme	YES	OR's officer	
NEXA	Training/workshop	YES	YES	The full recipe for developing successful grant applications in Horizon Europe Days	YES	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	
NEXA	Live Webinar	YES	YES	An introduction to Horizon Europe - Expert Insights	YES	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	

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Delivreable 4.3 - Common training programme for OR's R&I officers

Outermost Region:Madeira

Name of the WP4 Regional Coordinator:

FW partner	Type of capacity action	In the context of the FW GA (Yes/No)	Implemented? (Yes/No)	Name/title of the Capacity action	Specific for OR's Officer (or also for other actors in R&I ecosystem)?	Key words - Goal & Skills to be attained
ARDITI	Webinar	yes	yes	Perspetivas do Horizonte Europa (2021-2027) e a relação com os Grupos Temáticos no projeto FORWARD	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	
ARDITI	Trainings/workshops on project management and development: 1st training Session	yes	No	O Horizonte Europa e a elaboração de Candidaturas a projetos Europeus	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Knowledge Collaboration + Task management for more competitive participation in framework programs.
UMa	Trainings/workshops on project management and development: 2nd training Session	yes	No	O Horizonte Europa e a elaboração de Candidaturas a projetos Europeus	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Knowledge Collaboration + Task management for more competitive participation in framework programs.
ARDITI	Workshops for proposal co-creation and project implementation	yes	No	Horizon Europe: Funding opportunities in the European Framework Programs	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Knowledge + Coopetition + Finance for more competitive participation in framework programs

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				for Research & Innovation		
UMa	- Workshops for proposal co-creation and project implementation	yes	No	Horizon Europe: Funding opportunities in the European Framework Programs for Research & Innovation	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	Knowledge + Coopetition + Finance for more competitive participation in framework programs.
ARDITI	- Trainings on Entrepreneurship & Innovation	yes	No	N/a	OR's officer + actors in R&I ecosystem	N/a
UMa	- Seminar: Scientific Excellence in Research	yes	No	Rethinking 'Smart' Islands towards Self-Aware and Cooperative Islands	No	Knowledge Awareness Critical Thinking + Coopetition

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Delivreable 4.3 - Common training programme for OR's R&I officers

Outermost Region: Mayotte

Name of the WP4 Regional Coordinator: Hadel Laou Madi

FW partner	Type of capacity action	In the context of the FW GA (Yes/No)	Implemented? (Yes/No)	Name/title of the Capacity action	Specific for OR's Officer (or also for other actors in R&I ecosystem)?	Key words - Goal & Skills to be attained
CDM	Workshop/webinar training	yes	no	Atelier sur le management de projet de recherche	OR officers and other actors	Introduction to Horizon Europe; Management and coordination of EC-funded projects;
CDM	Workshop/webinar training	yes	no	Atelier sur la co-création et mise en œuvre de projets de recherche	OR officers and other actors	Increase the participation in FP; e.g. writing successful R&I proposals; how to find EU opportunities;
CDM	Webinar training			Comment intégrer les réseaux européens de recherche	OR officers & Researchers	Capacity building for networking and connectivity with EU clusters
CDM	Webinar training			Innovation et coopération entre les acteurs de R&D	R&I actors (both public & private)	Further analysis of the ability for business innovation opportunities and to contribute for the definition strategies to incorporate R&D for an ongoing/active business innovative processes and corporate policy. EU approach on funding for companies and European programs, opportunities and challenges for regional companies.

Delivreable 4.3 - Common training programme for OR's R&I officers

Outermost Region: St. Martine

Name of the WP4 Regional Coordinator: Rudy Lake

FW partner	Type of capacity action	In the context of the FW GA (Yes/No)	Implemented? (Yes/No)	Name/title of the Capacity action	Specific for OR's Officer (or also for other actors in R&I ecosystem)?	Key words - Goal & Skills to be attained
St. Martine	Webinar training	yes	no	Introduction to EU Funding	OR officers and other actors	A better knowledge about financing projects via European funds and how they work step by step
St. Martine	Webinar training	yes	no	The importance of taking part in a consortium	OR officers and other actors	Developing your network

Delivreable 4.3 - Common training programme for OR's R&I officers

Outermost Region:Martinique

Name of the WP4 Regional Coordinator: Philippe Hunel

FW partner	Type of capacity action	In the context of the FW GA (Yes/No)	Implemented? (Yes/No)	Name/title of the Capacity action	Specific for OR's Officer (or also for other actors in R&I ecosystem)?	Key words - Goal & Skills to be attained
Martinique Region	Webinar/workshops	yes	no	Presentation of the H2020 program and specific programs	OR's officers +companies+actors in R I	Carry out a project that meets the requirements of the European Commission, understand the rules of participation, the Horizon Europe procedures
Martinique Region	Webinar/workshops	yes	no	Editing, monitoring, evaluation of calls for projects	OR's officers +companies+actors in R I	the main stages of setting up the file
Martinique Region	Webinar/workshops	Yes	no	Create and organize your consortium and your project idea	OR's officers +companies+actors in R I	Establish a network and a consortium